

THE USAGE OF NONVERBAL MEANS IN DIALOGUE

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Abstract

The article focuses on the usage of nonverbal means and their features and advantages in dialogical speech as well as the functions of non-verbal means in dialogic speech. The author, on the basis of literature and her professional experience, describes the role of nonverbal means in communication and importance of using nonlinguistic signs in dialogic speech. The speech activity of a person is valid in three ways: speaking, reading and cooperation. Talking means that the speaker gives information, advises, and asks about unknown things. While speaking, the speaker's knowledge, culture, morals and manners are identified. Nonverbal means play an important role in the literary text. Their function is manifested in the expression of human inner feelings, attitudes to others. But in communication, a person's attitude to the external environment, to show something, to explain, to express his opinion, is culturally different. Also, nonverbal means that reflect human inner feelings are innate and universal, and culturally differentiated gestures are related to human behavior, upbringing, living environment, and culture, since they can be conditionally called natural and social nonverbal means.

Keywords

nonverbal means, verbal means, gestures, facial expressions, addressee, universal, information, communication, dialogue, kinesics.

INTRODUCTION.

In the process of globalization in world linguistics, the focus is on the functionality of language, which leads to an increase in the study of the process of communication in close connection with extra linguistic and paralinguistic means. Such social influence of language, in turn, raises the problem of studying the importance of nonverbal means in dialogic speech and in this context, it is important to study the advantages of nonverbal means in the process of dialogic speech, the pragmatic features of nonverbal means in the speech process, pragmatic

contradictions in intercultural nonverbal communication on the basis of modern linguistic analysis.

According to the nature of the means in use, different ways of transmitting information can be divided into two groups: verbal (verbal) and nonverbal (nonverbal). In the first case, the message is transmitted through language units through auditory or visual channels. In the second case, the information is transmitted by means of paralinguistic means - non-linguistic units "included in the voice message and transmitting semantic information". The role of verbal means in the transmission of cognitive information is enormous. B.F.Porshneva's statement that "The linguistic equivalent for every word and every sentence in our modern speech can be a word, a phrase, a broad text, or a paralinguistic sign" suggests that verbal and nonverbal means are interdependent concepts [7;151].

Non-verbal communication is a type of non-verbal communication between the speaker and the listener, which is used to supplement the verbal means. It is optional and non-optional and includes all message units except words. The nonverbal means confirms verbal communication, reflects the expressive attitude of speaking to an opinion that is expressed. In addition, during speech, the addressee receives pragmatic information from the addresser through non-verbal means.

In linguistics, various terms such as "Nonverbal means", "Extra linguistic means", "Paralinguistic means" are used in relation to the participation in sign, hand, eye, eyebrow, body movement, without the participation of words in the entrance of a person to contact. The Extra linguistics is understood that speech is accompanied by pauses, as well as various mental states of a person, such as crying, coughing, laughter, snoring. The Paralinguistic effect is the factors that adorn, strengthen or weaken the speech. This includes whether the speech is expressed in high or low volume, articulation, sounds, pauses, stuttering, coughing, tongue movements, and cries [12].

It should also be noted that every nonverbal means used in the communication process is subject to a pragmatic goal to ensure normality. "A gesture is any specific activity that is seen as part of the process of expressing or speaking an idea. This activity should have a communicative function"[4;134]. In every communication, the speaker aims to influence the person to whom the speech is directed. Nonverbal means exacerbate this effect. In particular, in the novel "Bygone days" the combination of verbal and nonverbal means is obvious. In the play, Arabic words are also found in the plates depicting nonverbal actions. In the play, Arabic words reflect the worldview of the characters, national traditions in the description of the behavior of brides pouring tea, which has become a habit in

the life of our people. In the novel, Otabek and his mother react to these actions in two different ways, such as getting up, bowing to her mother-in-law and Otabek, and handing over the bowl. This attitude is expressed through nonverbal actions:

"After milk tea, tea was brought in the kettle. Zaynab poured the first bowl, stood up, and handed it to her mother-in-law with both hands, filling the second bowl and trying to stand up, but Otabek stopped her.

"After that, don't stand up and just sit down to give tea," he said. "You can give it while sitting."

However, the mother-in-law did not like this, she protested:

"Why do you say that, boy?" Giving tea on the spot is the adornment of human beings, and brides are just brides, it is a bridal affair!

"I don't want her to sit down and give you tea for you;" but I do not need this offer, he said, and emptied the tea in his hand frequently. After reciting the Fatiha, he stood up and said, "Of course, she should stand up and give you tea ..." and left... (A. Qodiriy, "Bygone days").

The contextual situation is important in the use of nonverbal means in accordance with verbal means. For the correct understanding of the proposition expressed through the sentence and accompanying gestures, all the participants of the speech should be aware of the contextual situation. It can be noted that non-verbal means can convey the message without verbal means through direct visual-signal representations of linguistic means, but since it is not possible to see non-verbal action in written texts directly, we get information about non-verbality with the help of linguistic units:

"Are you Mirzakarimboy"

After the old man nodded, the young man continued:" I have come from the village of Khojakent; I am your nephew's son..." (Oybek. "Great blood". P.3).

It can be seen that the speaker (old man) confirmed the listener (young man) by nodding his head instead of saying "yes". In addition, it is convenient to use non-verbal means without using linguistic units in certain situations (if the noise is strong or the listener is far away and it is not possible to use verbal means) by the participants of the speech process.

Dialogue is one of the forms of speech in which every thought is directed directly to the interlocutor. Dialogue is distinguished by the brevity of thoughts. It contains only the essentials for the continuation of the conversation and does not elaborate on the events, but also consists of question-and-answer, discussion, various actions and exchange of ideas[13].

Dialogue can take place not only between two people, but also between any number of people [14]. Dialogue is widespread in ancient literature and used in the works of Greek philosophers and writers such as Cicero, Sineica, Reutarchus, Tacitus, Socrates, Plato, Aristotle [5;12]. It can also be seen in the studies of M. Buber, D. Bohm, M. Bakhtin, D. Nikulin, U. Lafasov, D. Babaeva, F. Karimova in world and Uzbek linguistics [6].

M.Bakhtin says that dialogue is understanding, monologue is explanation. He also notes that dialogue is an exchange of ideas based on understood information, and it can consist of an addresser, an addressee and a third person (super-

addressee)[1;318].

It is known that the dialogue consists of question-answer, discussion, reflection and discussion, and this situation is not observed in the monologue, but in the polylogue these things happen by the participants. Also, if we take into account the number of participants, even in a monologue, the addressee can speak to several participants, but the monologue is characterized by the fact that it does not require a response to the speech being expressed, it shows the inner feelings of the speaker, and often consists of rhetorical interrogative sentences. From the mentioned considerations, we can note that since the feature of polylogical speech is similar to dialogue, it can also be called dialogue.

In the process of dialogue, people exchange ideas with each other, get various information. Accordingly, Buber emphasized that dialogue can consist not only of words, but also of silence and various actions (gestures) [2;20].

At this point, the non-verbal means that serve to convey certain information in the dialogue process can be classified as follows:

1. **Visual means:** kinesics – hand, head, foot, body movements, stepping; facial expression, eye expression; stature, posture; direction of gaze, visual communication; skin reactions – redness, paleness, sweating; proxemics (time and space of communication) – distance with the interlocutor, distance angle, personal latitudes; additional means of communication – exaggerating or hiding physical characteristics (gender, age, race); changing the natural body structure (clothing, hairstyle, cosmetics, glasses, jewelry, tattoos, mustache and beard, small items in the hand).

2. Acoustic means: paralinguistic – sound quality, its range, tonality, pitch, timbre; extralinguistic – speech pauses, laughter, crying, sighing, coughing, clapping.

3. Tactile means: takesics – touch, handshake.

4. Olfactory means: pleasant, unpleasant smells; natural and artificial odors emitted by humans.

5. Silent. In addition, among non-verbal means, silence also plays an important role in dialogic speech. According to scientists, silence has its own meaning in different peoples. In particular, Satoshi Ishii and Tom Bruneau have pointed out that there are different types of silence in the world [3;114]. For example, Japanese and other nationalities remain silent when expressing displeasure or simply respect for the interlocutor, as well as in response to the unconditional love of a loved one. American and western people prefer to talk more in such situations. In Uzbeks, silence means consent and admission of guilt.

Linguists have interpreted the functions of nonverbal means differently. In particular, V.P.Konetskaya notes that nonverbal means, like verbal means, perform their main functions, such as communicative-informative, as well as special functions, such as pragmatic and expressive, which are activated in different situations [9;124]. The informative function provides information about an object or person, their characteristics, activities, and location. The pragmatic direction performs the following specific functions: communication and feedback, self-introduction, social orientation, incentive, and control functions. Expression functions include functions such as sensitivity, emotion, and flexibility.

It should also be noted that some linguists have also noted the syntactic functions of nonverbal means. For example, I.N.Gorelov and K.F.Sedov point out those nonverbal parts of communication can perform the functions of parts of speech: possessive, adverbial modified, predicate, direct and indirect complement [10;56]. In addition, according to N.V.Nakashidze, in the process of communication, nonverbal means perform communicative functions, such as those that accompany linguistic means in the speech process and individual users in the speech process [11;133]: The scientist distinguished the functions of nonverbal means in the general case according to their activity. Although these functions are easy to describe, they do not fully explain the functions of nonverbal means in speech.

In our study, nine functions of nonverbal means were revealed through examples taken from literary texts:

Function between individuals: nonverbal means serve to express inner feelings in interpersonal relationships.

Symbolic function: mainly gestures are used to convey a specific message. In dialogic speech, the addressee uses nonverbal means to convey the goal he or she is trying to convey to the addressee, and the addressee can understand what the addressee means through these nonverbal actions.

Visual function: In dialogic speech, nonverbal means are used to indicate the size, shape, distance, etc. of something. It also provides information about the identity of the interlocutor, his temperament, social status, his belonging to a particular culture or group, his personal qualities and characteristics, his emotional state in a particular situation.

Flexible function: Used as a means of confidence, self-comfort; often unintentional activities, such as playing with hair, stroking the beard, talking with a pen or cigarette.

Emphasis: Nonverbal tools often emphasize certain parts of a verbal message. For example, raising an eyebrow is a surprise; finger wagging protest; eyebrow twitching represents anger, dislike, or amazement.

Complementary: Nonverbal communication also reinforces the overall tone or attitude of verbal communication. For example, a state of lowering of the head or a state of depression may be accompanied by words expressing sadness; standing, smiling, and animated movement accompany the verbal expression of joy.

Contradiction: Nonverbal communication denies a verbal message, sometimes voluntarily, sometimes involuntarily, for example, can tell friends and family members that they are in good condition, even if they have tears in their eyes and a trembling voice.

Repetition: nonverbal means can return information transmitted by verbal means. In this case, the nonverbal means do not provide additional information to the message or convey new meaning.

Verbal means substitute: Nonverbal means can replace verbal means, for example, you can shake your head to confirm the message or show the rest of the fingers in the palm of your hand by raising your thumb up to praise.

CONCLUSION.

Non-verbal means can perform several tasks in dialogic speech. In the process of communication, non-verbal means can replace, supplement, repeat or completely contradict verbal means. It can also be noted that in dialogical speech, non-verbal means accompany verbal means and serve to make the speech meaningful and reliable. If non-verbal means are used in dialogic speech based on the psychological state, knowledge and skills of the addressee and the addressee, the speech will be meaningful and free of misunderstandings. Non-verbal means

can be conditionally divided into two groups: companions of linguistic means and groups such as specific manifestations of linguistic means. It is known that non-verbal means can convey the message without verbal means through direct visual-signal representations of linguistic means, but since it is not possible to directly see non-verbal action in written texts, it is possible to get information about non-verbal with the help of verbal means.

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